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● Studies on spider nomenclature – I: miscellaneous notes on unrecognisable species, new synonyms, and untenable subspecies (Araneae: Araneomorphae)

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Abstract: Miscellaneous notes on the nomenclature of spiders are presented, resultant are: 6 new synonymies; 7 subspecies raised to, and 2 restored to, species level; 40 taxa are proposed as *nomina dubia*; 1 subspecies is declared a *subspecies inquirenda*, and 112 species described based on juvenile type material are proposed as *species inquirendae*.

Keywords: *nomen dubium*, restored, revised status, *species inquirenda*, synonymy

● 蜘蛛命名研究 I：关于无法识别的种类、新异名以及难以维持亚种的多项注解（蛛形目：新蛛亚目）

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摘要：本文对多种蜘蛛的命名问题进行了注解，结果如下：提出 6 个新异名；7 个亚种提升至种级水平，2 个亚种恢复到种级水平；40 个种级分类单位被建议作为疑名对待；1 个亚种被视为待考亚种，另外 112 个以幼体作为模式标本进行描述的物种被提议为待考种。

关键词：疑名，恢复，修订地位，待考种，异名

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● Introduction

As the number of spider species described continues to rise each year (World Spider Catalog 2024), little attention is being placed on many old, forgotten names described in the previous two centuries. Equally, some more recent taxa have also been ignored due to their ‘problematic’ nature. Species described from juveniles, for instance, lack the most critical morphological characters for species differentiation in spiders – fully-developed genitalia. Despite this, hundreds of names remain valid described based on such specimens. Worse are descriptions from the nineteenth and twentieth centuries where the sex of the specimen and sometimes even the country of origin is not even known, and the provided description could apply to several, or many, taxa.

In this work, I deal with 168 names that I have come across in the last decade during the course of my arachnological research which can be dealt with efficiently, nomenclaturally. This represents just the first step in tackling the burden of enigmatic historical taxa, with many thousands described with good type localities and from adult specimens, which remain near equally poorly-known and still waiting to be redescribed. Spider taxonomists should be careful not to consider the establishment of new names (and description of new species), as more important than addressing congeneric historical taxa beforehand. Generic placement of taxa in this work is based on their status in the World Spider Catalog (2024) at the time of writing. Abbreviations: **IBSP** = Instituto Butantan, São Paulo, Brazil; **MCZ** = Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University, Cambridge, United States; **MNHN** = Muséum national d’Histoire naturelle, Paris, France; **MZUF** = Museo Zoologico La Specola, Università di Firenze, Florence, Italy; **NHMUK** = Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom; **NHMW** = Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Vienna, Austria; **OUMNH** = Oxford University Museum of Natural History, Oxford, United Kingdom; **USNMNT** = United States National Museum, Washington D.C., United States; **ZMB** = Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin.

● *Nomina dubia*

Family Actinopodidae Simon, 1892

Actinopus pertyi Lucas, 1843 *nomen dubium*

Fig. 1

Actinopus pertyi Lucas, 1843: 318 (♀).

Actinopus pertyi: Lucas 1845: 57, pl. 1, fig. 1 (♀).

Sphodros pertyi: Walckenaer 1847: 372.

Actinopus pertyi: Miglio, Pérez-Miles & Bonaldo 2020: 13 (*species inquirenda*).

Remarks. Lucas (1843: 318) described this species from “Nova-Hollandae” [= Australia] but later corrected the distribution to be “l’Amérique du nord” [= North America] in 1845 (Lucas 1845: 60). Walckenaer (1847: 372) simply gives the distribution as “D’Amérique” [= the Americas]. The plate provided by Lucas (1845) [no illustrations were given in Lucas (1843)] undoubtedly shows this specimen is correctly placed in the genus *Actinopus* Perty, 1833 (Fig. 1). Nonetheless, none of the aforementioned three works provide enough information to be able to differentiate this species from the more than one-hundred congeners known today (World Spider Catalog 2024). Miglio *et al.* (2020: 12–13) treated *A. pertyi* as a *species inquirenda* and stated: “The type of *A. pertyi* Lucas, 1843, originally deposited at Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle (MNHN), Paris is lost”. I concur with their statement, having made an unsuccessful search for this type material at the museum. The totally unknown type locality and absence of type material for examination renders this species unrecognisable. The general description, which does not distinguish it from any other *Actinopus*, also precludes a reasonable neotype designation in my opinion, as any choice of a true South American morphospecies would be arbitrary. Therefore, I propose *Actinopus pertyi* as a *nomen dubium*.

FIGURE 1. *Actinopus pertyi* Lucas, 1843 *nomen dubium*, original illustrations (and lettering thereof) from description by Lucas (1843).

Family Anyphaenidae Bertkau, 1878

Gayenna sigillum Mello-Leitão, 1941 *nomen dubium*

Gayenna sigillum Mello-Leitão, 1941: 194 (imm.).

Gayenna sigillum: Ramírez 2003: 225.

Remarks. As stated by Ramírez (2003), this Argentinian species has characteristics, and a distribution, congruent with that of *Oxysoma saccatum* (Tullgren 1902). However, the type material is immature (M. Ramírez pers. comm.) and it is not possible to distinguish juveniles at the species level within this genus. Therefore, due to the immaturity of the holotype, I propose *Gayenna sigillum* as a *nomen dubium*.

Family Araneidae Clerck, 1757

Araneus isabella (Vinson, 1863) *nomen dubium*

Epeira isabella Vinson, 1863: 157, 308, pl. 4, fig. 2 (imm.).

Remarks. The whereabouts of the type material is unknown and it is presumed lost, this, combined with the fact immature araneids are typically not taxonomically informative, and the absence of a precise type locality within Madagascar itself (Vinson 1863), renders this species unrecognisable. Therefore, I propose *Araneus isabella* as a *nomen dubium*.

Araneus metellus (Strand, 1907) *nomen dubium*

Aranea metella Strand, 1907b: 193 (imm.).

Remarks. This species was described based on immature material from China and the description does not give characters useful for differentiating this species from (adult) specimens of other known congeners (Strand 1907b). Furthermore, the type material was destroyed during Second World War bombing raids (Renner 1988). Thus, for these reasons, I propose *Araneus metellus* as a *nomen dubium*.

Araneus ocellatulus* (Roewer, 1942) *nomen dubium

Epeira ocellata O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1889: 29, pl. 6, fig. 17 (imm., preoccupied name).

Aranea ocellata: F. O. Pickard-Cambridge 1904: 518.

Araneus ocellatus: Petrunkevitch 1911: 307.

Aranea ocellatula: Roewer 1942: 849 (replacement name).

Remarks. After searching the collections, it is apparent to me that the type material of this Guatemalan species is not in the Oxford University Museum of Natural History and is thus lost. The original description gives no characters which differentiate this species from congeners or are known to be stable in respect to ontogeny (O. Pickard-Cambridge 1889). Therefore, I propose *Araneus ocellatulus* as a *nomen dubium*.

Araneus transversivittiger* (Strand, 1907) *nomen dubium

Aranea transversivittigera Strand, 1907b: 180 (imm.).

Remarks. As for *Araneus metellus*, this species was described based on immature type material from China, now lost (Renner 1988), and the original description gives no characters of use (Strand 1907b). Therefore, I propose *Araneus transversivittiger* as a *nomen dubium*.

Cyrtarachne sinicola* Strand, 1942 *nomen dubium

Cyrtarachne sp.: Schenkel 1936: 127, fig. 46 (imm.).

Cyrtarachne sinicola Strand, 1942: 396 (imm.).

Remarks. Strand (1942) ascribed an available name to this species which was, correctly, named cautiously as “*Cyrtarachne* sp.” by Schenkel (1936) on the basis it was immature. Furthermore, the type locality Szechuan [= Sichuan] comprises a large area of China, a country known for significant short-range endemism in large amounts of its spider fauna. The species is not recognisable from the original description as most characters given (Schenkel, 1936) could be subject to ontogeny. Therefore, based on the above reasons, I propose *Cyrtarachne sinicola* as a *nomen dubium*.

Family Corinnidae Karsch, 1880***Corinna haemorrhoea* (Bertkau, 1880) *nomen dubium***

Liocranum haemorrhoum Bertkau, 1880: 47 (imm.).

Corinna haemorrhoea: Mello-Leitão 1922: 54.

Remarks. The type material for this species from Brazil is lost (Jason Dunlop, Bernhard Huber, and Peter Jäger pers. comm.) and the description alone (Bertkau 1880) is not sufficient to distinguish it from other corinnids known from the general area. Therefore, I propose *Corinna haemorrhoea* as a *nomen dubium*.

Corinna selysi* (Bertkau, 1880) *nomen dubium

Hypsinotus selysii Bertkau, 1880: 111 (imm.).

Corinna selysi: Petrunkevitch 1911: 469.

Remarks. Similarly to *C. haemorrhoea*, the type material of this Brazilian species is lost and the description (Bertkau 1880) renders it unrecognisable. Therefore, I propose *Corinna selysi* as a *nomen dubium*.

Family Ctenidae Keyserling, 1877***Ctenus bicolor* (Bertkau in Van Beneden, 1880) *nomen dubium***

Isoctenus bicolor Bertkau in Van Beneden, 1880: 637.

Ctenus bicolor: F. O. Pickard-Cambridge 1902: 412.

Remarks. The description of this spider gives no clue as to which sex it belongs and if indeed it was adult. There are no figures, and the type material is lost (Jason Dunlop, Bernhard Huber, and Peter Jäger pers. comm.).

The holotype was a stowaway, imported into Belgium with bromeliads from Brazil, although it is not known precisely from what part of Brazil the plants were from (see Van Beneden 1880). Therefore, since this species has an inadequate original description and the type material is lost, I thus propose *Ctenus bicolor* as a ***nomen dubium***.

Ctenus walckenaerii* Griffith, 1833 *nomen dubium

Fig. 2

Ctenus walckenaerii Griffith, 1833: 538, pl. 3, fig. 2.

Remarks. This species has no stated type locality in the original description. Indeed, the description is less than 10 words long. The index to the plates (Griffith 1833: 538) includes the statement “3. 2. *Ctenus Walckenaerii*, 426 Yellowish, marked with reddish and black lines.” which indicates: the identity of the spider in figure 2 of plate 3, followed by the name of the spider, the page number on which it is mentioned [really only the genus *Ctenus* Walckenaer, 1805 itself is mentioned in broad terms in the main text] and a one-sentence description which ultimately makes this name available from Griffith’s work. The illustration in Griffith (1833) appears to indeed show a ctenid, but its generic affinity is not possibly to decipher from the information available alone. Furthermore, whilst the World Spider Catalog (2024) lists the holotype as being male, the illustration suggests it was instead not an adult male, rather either a female or immature specimen of either sex (Fig. 2). The sex is never indicated in the description by Griffith (1833). Given the absence of a type locality, minimalist original description, and the fact that no type material is known to exist, I propose *Ctenus walckenaerii* as a ***nomen dubium***.

FIGURE 2. *Ctenus walckenaerii* Griffith, 1833 ***nomen dubium***, original illustration (including original numbering) from description by Griffith (1833).

Family Gnaphosidae Banks, 1892

Pterotricha linnaei (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium*

Fig. 3A

Drassus linnaei Audouin, 1826: 384, pl. 5, fig. 7 (♀).

Pythonissa linnaei: Simon 1878: 205.

Pterotricha linnaei: Reimoser 1919: 173.

Remarks. The types of all species described by Audouin (1826) are presumed lost (see Sherwood 2022). Only the habitus of this Egyptian gnaphosid is figured (see Fig. 3A), and the description (Audouin 1826) is insufficient to recognise the species. Therefore, I propose *Pterotricha linnaei* as a *nomen dubium*.

FIGURE 3. Original drawings (A–F) accompanying descriptions of six species by Audouin (1826) treated herein: **A** *Pterotricha linnaei* (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium* **B** *Zelotes listeri* (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium* **C** *Arctosa nilotica* (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium* **D** *Aelurillus dorthesi* (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium* **E** *Pellenes frischi* (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium* **F** *Xysticus clercki* (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium*.

Zelotes listeri* (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium

Fig. 3B

Drassus listeri Audouin, 1826: 155, pl. 5, fig. 4 (♀).*Macaria listeri*: Simon 1864: 113.*Prothesima listeri*: Simon 1878: 98.

Remarks. As for *Pterotricha linnaei*, the type is lost and only the habitus drawing (see Fig. 3B) and a general written description is available (Audouin 1826), this Egyptian species is not able to be distinguished from known congeners. Therefore, I propose *Zelotes listeri* as a *nomen dubium*.

Family Halonoproctidae Pocock, 1901***Ummidia armata* (Ausserer, 1875) *nomen dubium****Pachylomerus armatus* Ausserer, 1875: 143 (♀).

Remarks. The description of this species by Ausserer (1875) is not sufficient to differentiate it from congeners and the type locality is unknown. I have been unable to locate holotype in the Natural History Museum, London (NHMUK) or the Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (NHMW), the two museums which house what survives of the Ausserer collection, despite making dedicated searches for this specimen whilst at both museums. Therefore, I consider this species unrecognisable and propose *U. armata* as a *nomen dubium*.

Family Idiopidae Simon, 1889***Idiops neglectus* L. Koch in Ausserer, 1875 *nomen dubium****Idiops neglectus* L. Koch in Ausserer, 1875: 146 (♀).

Remarks. Much like the preceding species, the description of this unlocalised species (see Ausserer 1875) does not differentiate this species from congeners, indeed it leaves doubt even at the family-level identification. I have been unable to locate the type material in NHMUK or NHMW, nor is it listed in the collections of any of the primary zoological museums in Germany (where Koch was resident), and therefore consider this species with no known country of origin to be unrecognisable. Thus, I propose *Idiops neglectus* as a *nomen dubium*.

Family Linyphiidae Blackwall, 1859***Ceratinopsis bicolor* Banks, 1896 *nomen dubium***

Fig. 4A, B

Ceratinopsis bicolor Banks, 1896: 67 (imm. ♀).*Ceratinopsis bicolor*: Bishop & Crosby 1930: 19.

Remarks. Banks (1896) described this species based on immature female syntypes from Ithaca, New York, United States. One of the syntypes in the Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard (MCZ) has been digitised (Fig. 4A, B). The pathway of epigynal development in *Ceratinopsis* Emerton, 1882 shows large interspecific variation as is common in linyphiids (Fig. 4C–J) and thus the pre-epigyne is not informative. However, it cannot even be certain that this species is conspecific with *Ceratinopsis*. Indeed, nine decades ago the dubious status of this species was already remarked upon by Bishop & Crosby (1930: 19) who went much further: “The types of this species in the Museum of Comparative Zoology are two recently hatched specimens that probably do not even belong to the family. The species cannot be recognized from the description. Banks states his specimens were immature”. I concur with Bishop & Crosby (1930) that the species is unrecognisable, even from reference to the types, although tentatively maintain it as a linyphiid. Nonetheless, for the reasons proposed above, *Ceratinopsis bicolor* is proposed as a *nomen dubium*.

FIGURE 4. *Ceratinopsis bicolor* Banks, 1896 *nomen dubium* (A–B) and the epigynes of some other known species of *Ceratinopsis* Emerton, 1882 in ventral view (C–I): **A** habitus, dorsal view **B** undeveloped genital area, ventral view **C** *Ceratinopsis auriculata* Emerton, 1909 **D** *Ceratinopsis bona* Chamberlin & Ivie, 1944 **E** *Ceratinopsis interpres* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1874) (type species) **F** *Ceratinopsis laticeps* Emerton, 1882 **G** *Ceratinopsis nigriceps* Emerton, 1882 **H** *Ceratinopsis nigripalpis* Emerton, 1882 **I** *Ceratinopsis sylvania* Chamberlin & Ivie, 1944. Figs A–H by the Field Museum of Natural History, Creative Commons, CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial) 4.0. Fig. I by Marc Milne, Creative Commons, CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial) 4.0. See: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/deed.en>.

Erigonella groenlandica* Strand, 1905 *nomen dubium

Erigonella groenlandica Strand, 1905: 26 (imm.).

Remarks. This species was described based on an immature specimen from Greenland. Brændegaard (1936) later noted the holotype was deposited in what is now the Naturhistorisk Museum, Oslo, Norway and considered it as a distinct species but, equally, noted its establishment based on a juvenile was not good practice. Thaler (1971: 312) considered this species as a “nicht zu deuten” (today interpreted as *nomen dubium*) and notes that specimens other than the type were not found by future workers. Indeed, this remains true as of today. Vanden Borre *et al.* (2003) cite Thaler (1971) also considering the species dubious. The designation of Thaler (1971) has been overlooked by the World Spider Catalog (2024) and thus *E. groenlandica* remains a valid species until the present contribution. It is clear that for over 120 years the identity of this species has been doubtful, and the name is unrecognisable. Thus, based on the immaturity of the holotype and uninformative characters given in its original description, *Erigonella groenlandica* is proposed as a *nomen dubium*.

Family Lycosidae Sundevall, 1833***Arctosa nilotica* (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium***

Fig. 3C

Lycosa nilotica Audouin, 1826: 369, pl. 4, fig. 7 (♀).*Lycosa perita*: Simon 1876: 276 (syn.).*Lycosa nilotica*: Simon 1907a: 8 (*contra* Simon 1876).*Lycosa nilotica*: Simon, 1937: 1139 (suspected syn. of *Arctosa variana* C. L. Koch, 1847 [as *Lycosa variana*]).*Arctosa nilotica*: Bonnet 1955: 655.

Remarks. The type material of taxa described by Audouin are all presumed lost (see Sherwood 2022). This species was described without illustrations of the genitalia, with only the habitus presented (see Fig. 3C). The description and aforementioned illustration do not adequately distinguish this species from congeners, of which several occur in Egypt (Marusik & Nadolny 2020). Therefore, for these reasons, I propose *Arctosa nilotica* as a *nomen dubium*.

Family Oxyopidae Thorell, 1869***Peucetia elegans* (Blackwall, 1864) *nomen dubium****Pasithea elegans* Blackwall, 1864: 39 (♀).

Remarks. The description of this Indian species is of a juvenile and provides no useful characters to differentiate it at the species level (Blackwall 1864). Furthermore, the type locality is simply ‘India’ without a precise location within the country specified and the type material is lost, since it is not present in at the Oxford University Museum of Natural History (OUMNH), where the entirety of the surviving collection of Blackwall is housed (rescued by O. Pickard-Cambridge who noted its incompleteness and later deposited it in Oxford). Therefore, I propose *Peucetia elegans* as a *nomen dubium*.

Family Philodromidae Thorell, 1869***Thanatus flavescens* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876 *nomen dubium****Thanatus flavescens* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876: 592 (imm.).*Tibellus flavescens*: Reimoser 1919: 125.

Remarks. As for *A. ocellatulus*, the type material of this Egyptian species described by O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876) is not in OUMNH (where his collection and that of John Blackwall now reside) and is consequently to be regarded as lost. Therefore, I propose *Thanatus flavescens* as a *nomen dubium*.

Family Salticidae Blackwall, 1841***Aelurillus dorthesi* (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium***

Fig. 3D

Attus dorthesii Audouin, 1826: 405, pl. 7, fig. 9 (♀).*Aelurops dorthesi*: Simon 1876: 139.*Aelurillus dorthesi*: Reimoser 1919: 111.

Remarks. The type material is lost (see Sherwood 2022). This Egyptian species was described without illustrations of the genitalia, with only the habitus presented (see Fig 3D). The description (Audouin 1826) is not sufficient to identify this species both at the species nor genus-level. Therefore, I propose *Aelurillus dorthesi* as a *nomen dubium*.

Pellenes frischi* (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium

Fig. 3E

Attus frischi Audouin, 1826: 406, pl. 7, fig. 11 (♀).*Pellenes fischeri*: Simon 1876: 101 (*lapsus calami, nomen nudum*).

Remarks. As for *Aelurillus dorthesi*, the description and sole (habitus, see Fig. 4E) illustration of this Egyptian species (Audouin 1826) do not permit its recognition, and the type is lost (see Sherwood 2022). Therefore, I propose *Pellenes frischi* as a *nomen dubium*.

Saitis signatus* (Keyserling, 1883) *nomen dubium

Fig. 5

Prostheclina signata Keyserling, 1883: 1464, pl. 123, fig. 6 (♀).*Saitis signatus*: Roewer 1955b: 1097.

Remarks. Keyserling (1883) does not mention a precise locality for this species (Fig. 5), although it is presumably from Oceania or Southeast Asia. The illustrations of the epigyne are not sufficient for splitting this species from congeners and the whereabouts of the type material is unknown. I searched the NHMUK where the vast majority of Keyserling's personal collection was donated and could not find this specimen. For these reasons, I propose *Saitis signatus* as a *nomen dubium*.

FIGURE 5. *Saitis signatus* (Keyserling, 1883) *nomen dubium*, original illustrations (and lettering thereof) from description by Keyserling (1883).

Family Tetragnathidae Menge, 1866***Tetragnatha chrysochlora* (Audouin, 1826) *nomen dubium****Eugnatha chrysochlora* Audouin, 1826: 324 (♀).*Tetragnatha chrysochlora*: Simon 1929: 750.

Remarks. No illustrations are provided for this Egyptian species, the type material is lost (see Sherwood 2022), and the original description (Audouin 1826) does not allow for the differentiation of this taxon from known congeners. Therefore, I propose *Tetragnatha chrysochlora* as a *nomen dubium*.

Tetragnatha shanghaiensis* Strand, 1907 *nomen dubium

Tetragnatha shanghaiensis Strand, 1907b: 150 (imm.).

Remarks. As given for several other species detailed above, Strand used immature type material for the description of this Chinese species, and it is not distinguishable from [adult] congeners. Strand's material was deposited in the Lübeck Museum and lost during bombing of that institute in the Second World War (Renner 1988; World Spider Catalog 2024). Therefore, this, in combination with the other reasons discussed above, I propose *Tetragnatha shanghaiensis* as a *nomen dubium*. It is of note that Strand (1907b: 149) first notes this species as “*Tetragnatha* sp.” but gives the manuscript name *Tetragnatha shanghaiensis* on the following page (Strand 1907b: 150). Most likely, he intended not to describe it as a new species, but I agree with the World Spider Catalog (2024) who listed it as a formal species description, since the paragraph before is explicitly giving a morphological description and the name was not proposed in any prior work. In 1907, descriptions were not subject to the requirement for explicitly giving nomina as new, as is found in zoological nomenclature today (ICZN 1999).

Family Theraphosidae Thorell, 1869***Aphonopelma hesperum* (Chamberlin, 1917) *nomen dubium***

Eurypelma hespera Chamberlin, 1917: 54 (imm.).

Aphonopelma hesperum: Smith 1995: 112, figs. 412–415 (imm.).

Remarks. The immature male holotype of *A. hesperum*, deposited in the Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University, is a typical specimen of *Aphonoepelma sensu lato* with no characters for which it can be differentiated from congeners. Chamberlin (1917: 54) described this species from “Mexico: West Coast” which covers a huge region of a country known for short-range endemism in its theraphosids (Hamilton *et al.* in prep.). Smith (1995: 112) conjectured that it was “probably collected from the lower California Baja peninsula” but gave no evidence for this statement which appears to be pure conjecture. The unknown type locality coupled with the immaturity of the specimen make it unidentifiable from morphology or biogeography, two crucial lines of evidence for identifying [adult] species of this genus. Therefore, I propose *Aphonopelma hesperum* as a *nomen dubium*.

Plesiopelma imperatrix* Piza, 1976 *nomen dubium

Plesiopelma imperatrix Piza, 1976: 3, fig. 1 (♀).

Eurypelma imperatrix: Brignoli 1983: 137.

Citharacanthus imperatrix: Platnick 1993: 103.

Remarks. This species has one of the shortest and least informative descriptions of any theraphosid described in the Twentieth Century. No potential distinguishing characters such as the spermathecae, leg scopulae, or any details of the presence/absence of stridulatory setae on any appendage are given. The type locality is simply ‘Brazil’, and the description of Piza (1976) could refer to very many theraphosids in Brazil. A single black-and-white photograph of the specimen aids little in identifying it below the subfamily level. Unfortunately, the holotype was lost during the fire at the Instituto Butantan, São Paulo (IBSP; Antonio Brescovit and Sylvia Lucas pers. comm.) and this, alongside the absence of a precise type locality, render it unable to be recognised. Therefore, I propose *Plesiopelma imperatrix* as a *nomen dubium*.

Of note, as shown in the synonymy list, two incongruent generic placements were given for this species in the large spider catalogues of Brignoli (1983) and Platnick (1993). The convoluted taxonomy of *Eurypelma* C. L. Koch, 1850 is outside the scope of this work. However, it is worth noting Platnick (1993) listed this species in *Citharacanthus* Pocock, 1901 because Raven (1985) proposed a synonymy of *Plesiopelma* Pocock, 1901 with *Citharacanthus* with no supporting evidence. Thankfully, this erroneous synonymy was rejected by Pérez-Miles *et al.* (1996).

Family Theridiidae Sundevall, 1833

Steatoda sagax (Blackwall, 1865) *nomen dubium*

Theridion sagax Blackwall, 1865: 93 (imm.).

Teutana sagax Simon 1883: 302.

Remarks. The type material of this species is lost (not present in OUMNH, see above), and the description gives no characters which can readily differentiate it from other theridiids (Blackwall 1865) within the general vicinity of the type locality (Cape Verde Islands). Therefore, I propose *Steatoda sagax* as a *nomen dubium*.

Theridion zonatum Eydoux & Souleyet, 1842 *nomen dubium*

Fig. 6

Theridion zonatum Eydoux & Souleyet, 1842: 290, pl. 1, figs 36–39.

Remarks. This species has no known type locality and may have been collected in any number of places during the circumnavigation of the globe by the corvette *La Bonite*. The description, including (Fig. 6, pink outlines) illustrations, do not allow for its recognition (Eydoux & Souleyet 1842). Thus, I propose *Theridion zonatum* as a *nomen dubium*.

FIGURE 6. Part of plate, showing illustrations of invertebrates, in Eydoux & Souleyet (1842), pink outlines = *Theridion zonatum* Eydoux & Souleyet, 1842 *nomen dubium*, purple outlines = *Thomisus cancroides* Eydoux & Souleyet, 1842 *nomen dubium*.

Family Thomisidae Sundevall, 1833

Camaricus hastifer (Percheron, 1833) *nomen dubium*

Fig. 7

Epeira hastifera Percheron, 1833: 1, pl. 4, figs a–c (♂).

Delena hastifera: Walckenaer 1837: 494.

Camaricus hastifer: Simon 1895: 1011.

Remarks. I concur with Simon (1895) that this species is well placed in *Camaricus* Thorell, 1887 as the description of Walckenaer (1837) – who redescribed the holotype – is sufficient to conclude this alongside examination of the plate in Percheron (1833). The colouration of *C. hastifer* is resemblant of [but not identical to] *C. formosus* Thorell, 1887, the type species, but this alone is not sufficient evidence for a synonymy because colouration is intraspecifically variable in several species of this genus (pers. obs.). There is no known type locality

and no known type repository. I made a preliminary search at MNHN in case this specimen was deposited there after the work of Walckenaer but did not locate this specimen. It indeed may never have been deposited in that collection or may be without labels and have been overlooked. Thus, we remain reliant only on the prior literature, which mostly show habitus and does not depict the male palp in conventional views (Fig. 7) and which lacks a type locality. Therefore, given these reasons above, I propose *Camaricus hastifer* as a ***nomen dubium***.

FIGURE 7. *Camaricus hastifer* (Percheron, 1833) ***nomen dubium***, original illustrations (and lettering thereof) from description by Percheron (1833).

Thomisus cancroides* Eydoux & Souleyet, 1842 ***nomen dubium**

Fig. 6

Thomisus cancroides Eydoux & Souleyet, 1842: 288, pl. 1, figs 40–43.

Remarks. The illustrations (Fig. 6, purple outlines) are sufficient to show it is a thomisid but not to differentiate it at the genus or species level. Given this, in conjunction with a totally unknown distribution (see above comments for *T. zonatum*), I propose *Thomisus cancroides* as a ***nomen dubium***.

Xysticus clercki* (Audouin, 1826) ***nomen dubium**

Fig. 3F

Thomisus clerckii Audouin, 1826: 398, pl. 6, fig. 13 (♀).

Xysticus clercki: Pavesi 1883: 63.

Remarks. The type is lost (see Sherwood 2022), only an illustration of the habitus (see Fig. 3F) and a vague general description (Audouin 1826) which could apply to a number of known congeners is available, therefore this Egyptian species is not recognisable. Thus, I propose *Xysticus clercki* as a ***nomen dubium***. The material assigned by Pavesi (1883) was done so provisionally, as he even commented (in Italian) that the figure from Audouin (1826) left ‘much to be desired’. This material, ironically, was not figured and I have as yet been able to trace its whereabouts. This alone, however, is not sufficient justification to keep the species valid, especially as there is nothing yet that guarantees this material is indeed conspecific with the name-bearing type seen by Audouin (1826).

Family Uloboridae Thorell, 1869

Uloborus canus MacLeay, 1827 *nomen dubium*

Uloborus canus MacLeay, 1827: 468.

Remarks. The holotype is lost (Helen Smith *in* World Spider Catalog 2024) and the description does not give sufficient characters to differentiate it from all other known congeners. No illustrations are provided in the original description nor a precise type locality within Australia at which it was taken (MacLeay 1827). It has remained undiscovered for nearly 100 years since its original description thus it seems unlikely it will be recognisable in the near future. Thus, I propose *Uloborus canus* as a *nomen dubium*.

Family Zodariidae Thorell, 1881

Cryptothele cristata Simon, 1884 *nomen dubium*

Cryptothele cristata Simon, 1884: 302 (imm. ♂).

Remarks. Simon (1884) described this species based on an immature male, supposedly from Mexico which is deposited in MNHN. As noted by the World Spider Catalog (2024), the *locus typicus* is likely to be erroneous and the description is not helpful in differentiating this species from other [adult] congeners as its characteristics may be a result of ontogeny. Therefore, I propose *Cryptothele cristata* as a *nomen dubium*.

Storena ornata (Bradley, 1877) *nomen dubium*

Habronestes ornatus Bradley, 1877: 119 (imm.).

Remarks. The whereabouts of the type material of this Australian species is unknown and presumed lost, not existing in any modern Australian collection to my knowledge, and certainly not in any of the museum collections consulted during this work, and the description of this specimen from non-adult material (Bradley 1877) means it is unrecognisable. Therefore, I propose *Storena ornata* as a *nomen dubium*.

● Synonymous species

Family Araneidae Clerck, 1757

Eriophora edax (Blackwall, 1863) = *Araneus unistriatus* (McCook, 1894) *syn. nov.*

Fig. 8

Epeira edax Blackwall, 1863: 30 (♂♀).

Verrucosa unistriata McCook, 1894: 201, pl. 5, fig. 3 (♀). *syn. nov.*

Eriophora edax: Banks 1909: 210.

Araneus edax: Petrunkevitch 1911: 290.

Araneus unistriatus: Petrunkevitch 1911: 322.

Aranea edax cauca Strand, 1916: 111 (♀).

Eriophora edax: Petrunkevitch 1930: 325, figs. 205–207 (♂♀).

Araneus argyronotus Mello-Leitão, 1939: 111, fig. 14 (♀).

Eriophora edax: Bryant 1948: 62, fig. 7 (♀).

Araniella geayi Caporiacco, 1954: 104, fig. 24 (♀).

Eriophora edax: Levi 1971: 296, figs. 35–48 (♂♀).

Araneus geayi: Levi 1974: 293.

Eriophora edax: Levi 1991: 177–178.

Eriophora edax: Levi 2002: 541, figs. 112–113 (♀).

Type material. Holotype ♀ (USNMENT 01968865), Fort Yuma, Arizona, United States, coll. George Marx, no. 268, type 1687.

FIGURE 8. *Eriphora edax* (Blackwall, 1863) – holotype female of *Araneus unistriatus* (McCook, 1894) **syn. nov.**: **A** habitus, dorsal view **B** same, ventral view **C** epigyne, ventral view (undissected) **D** associated labels. Photos by, and courtesy of, Tom Nguyen (USNMENT).

Remarks. McCook (1894) described this species from Fort Yuma, Arizona based on a specimen in the George Marx collection. The holotype (Fig. 8) is deposited in the National Museum of Natural History, Washington D.C. (USNMENT). Unfortunately, Marx is well known for ascribing erroneous localities to specimens he collected (e.g. Smith 1995). This seemed likely for this species because the World Spider Catalog (2024) notes the late Herb Levi (*in litt.*) as stating this species probably belongs to *Parawixia* F. O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904 and that its true locality is probably in Brazil. Nonetheless, whilst the epigyne of this species has similarities to *Parawixia audax* (Blackwall, 1863), *Parawixia bistriata* (Rengger, 1836) and *Parawixia undulata* (Keyserling, 1892), the colouration is not congruent. The true identity of this species is already transcribed on a label written by Levi in 1988 (Fig. 8D), the

colour pattern and epigyne are clearly that of *Eriophora edax* (Blackwall, 1863). However, this result was never published by Levi before his death. Therefore, I hereby propose *A. unistriatus* **syn. nov.** as a junior synonym of *E. edax*. Thus, it is also likely that this is a spider whose type locality was also, unusually for Marx, correct since *E. edax* occurs in both Arizona and neighbouring California.

● *Species inquirendae*

The species below are all described from juveniles and have almost all taxa not been found again since their original descriptions. However, their original descriptions along with their comparatively precise type localities give some chance for the collection of adult topotypes, and in most – but not all – cases I have been able to confirm their respective type material is extant (either by direct examination, or through consultation of catalogues, databases, and correspondence with various collection managers). Therefore, I prefer to be conservative with the below taxa and not risk being overzealous by designating them all *nomina dubia*, although colleagues are of course welcome to designate any of them as so if they find that the species is unrecognisable based on more thorough investigations.

Most of Simon's type material of species listed below should be deposited in MNHN; most of Strand's below species are in the Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin (ZMB) (World Spider Catalog 2024), except *Scotophaeus lamperti* Strand, 1906 and *Arctosa nyembeensis* (Strand, 1916) which are in the Museum Wiesbaden, Germany (Jäger 1998); the type material listed below of Dahl and Karsch are deposited in ZMB; that of Keyserling and Pocock in NHMUK; most of Caporiacco's types (but see paragraph below) are in the Museo Zoologico La Specola, Università di Firenze, Florence, Italy (MZUF) (Berdondini & Whitman 2003) – except those described in Caporiacco (1949) which are deposited in the Museo Civico di Storia Naturale, Verona, Italy (Ballarin *et al.* 2020), *Mallinella subinermis* Caporiacco, 1947 and *Hoplolathys aethiopica* Caporiacco, 1947 which are deposited in the Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest (Caporiacco 1947b), and that of *Hexommulocymus kolosvaryi* Caporiacco, 1955, *Odo drescoi* Caporiacco, 1955, and *Odo incertus* Caporiacco, 1955 in the Museo de Biología, Universidad Central de Venezuela, Caracas; that of Roewer, with one exception above (*Araneus ocellatulus* (Roewer, 1942)) and one below (see below paragraph), is in MZUF; that of Banks is in MCZ; that of Lawrence is in the Iziko South African Museum, Cape Town, South Africa; that of Schenkel (other than species addressed earlier in the manuscript) are in the Naturhistorisches Museum, Basel, Switzerland (World Spider Catalog 2024) except *Lycosa pavlovi* Schenkel, 1953 and *Lycosa russea* Schenkel, 1953 which should be in the Tianjin Natural History Museum, Tianjin, China; that of O. Pickard-Cambridge is in OUMNH; that of Montgomery is in the American Museum of Natural History, New York, United States (see Gertsch 1934); that of Becker is in the Royal Belgian institute of Natural Sciences, Brussels, Belgium, and all below species of L. Koch, except two, are in the Zoologisches Museum Hamburg (World Spider Catalog 2024), the exceptions being *Pardosa serena* (L. Koch, 1875) and *Trochosa praetecta* L. Koch, 1875 which are in ZMB (World Spider Catalog 2024).

The below type material described by Mello-Leitão should be deposited in the Museo de La Plata, Argentina, but this needs to be confirmed as some other [adult] type material supposed to be deposited in this institution is not present there (D. Ríos-Tamayo pers. comm.). Except for the two species described in Thorell (1895), which are in NHMUK, the rest of the below taxa described by Thorell appear to be in the Museo di Storia Naturale Giacomo Doria, Genoa, Italy, but I do not have a full list of material deposited in that institution, so cannot state this with certainty for every species. The type of *Urocteana poecilis* Roewer, 1961 should be deposited in the Section Entomologie des Institut Français d'Afrique Noire, Dakar, Senegal but I have been unable to confirm this. The type material of *Scortecchia termitarum* Caporiacco, 1936 is probably in the Museo Civico di Storia Naturale di Milano, Milan, Italy but, similarly, I have been unable to confirm this. The following other species are known not to be in the museums of Florence or Verona, but other museums have not responded to enquiries as to whether they are extant. Many smaller museums in Italy which have varying amounts of Caporiacco type material (F. Ballarin pers. comm.) so I prefer not to make any assumptions about the whereabouts of the types of the following species: *Castianeira brunellii* Caporiacco, 1940 (Corinnidae), *Poecilochroa pauciaculeis* Caporiacco, 1947 (Gnaphosidae),

Pterotrichina nova Caporiacco, 1934 (Gnaphosidae), *Stoliczka affinis* Caporiacco, 1935 (Pisauridae), *Senoculus guianensis* Caporiacco, 1947 (Senoculidae), *Argyrodes vatovae* (Caporiacco, 1940) (Theridiidae), *Euryopsis venutissima* (Caporiacco, 1934) (Theridiidae), *Firmicus strandi* Caporiacco, 1947 (Thomisidae), *Synema pauciaculeis* Caporiacco, 1947 (Thomisidae), *Xysticus multiaculeatus* Caporiacco, 1940 (Thomisidae), *Odo drescoi* (Caporiacco, 1955) (Xenoctenidae), and *Odo incertus* Caporiacco, 1955 (Xenoctenidae).

All cases of immature species (and genera) established in the Sparassidae are explicitly excluded here as all will be dealt with elsewhere by my colleagues Peter Jäger and Cristina Rheims. The family Salticidae has many species which are described from juveniles and some will be *nomina dubia*, however I will deal with the relevant species with collaborators separately from the present contribution. I have also excluded spiders I know to be dubious, but which belong to groups that I am aware currently under revision by colleagues and thus will be resolved by them (e.g. numerous spiders of the Yarkand Expedition currently being revised by Yuri Marusik and Zoë Simmons and *Copa lineata* Simon, 1903 (Corinnidae) which will be treated by Charles Haddad). Problematic species in the family Zodariidae, and all spiders from Australia, described from immatures are excluded for the same reason. Thus, this is not an exhaustive list of all spiders described from juveniles, just those where I am satisfied that rendering them *species inquirenda* and thereby bringing them to the attention of colleagues would be beneficial, as many names might be stabilised with dedicated work. Similarly, it is quite easy for any colleagues who wish to designate any of the names below as *nomina dubia* if they deem necessary during the course of genus or family-dedicated revisions.

Family Agelenidae C. L. Koch, 1837

Agelena incertissima Caporiacco, 1939 *species inquirenda*

Agelena incertissima Caporiacco, 1939: 315 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Family Araneidae Clerck, 1757

Araneus basalteus Schenkel, 1936 *species inquirenda*

Araneus basalteus Schenkel, 1936: 99, fig. 35 (imm.).

Distribution. China.

Araneus carabellus (Strand, 1913) *species inquirenda*

Aranea carabella Strand, 1913: 377 (imm.).

Distribution. Democratic Republic of the Congo.

Araneus pudicus (Thorell, 1898) *species inquirenda*

Epeira pudica Thorell, 1898: 358 (imm.).

Distribution. Myanmar.

Cyclosa pseudocolata Schenkel, 1936 *species inquirenda*

Cyclosa pseudocolata Schenkel, 1936: 124, fig. 44 (imm.).

Distribution. China.

Larinia strandi Caporiacco, 1941 *species inquirenda*

Larinia strandi Caporiacco, 1941: 103 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

***Poltys apiculatus* Thorell, 1893 species inquirenda**

Poltys apiculatus Thorell, 1893: 228 (imm.).

Distribution. Singapore.

***Poltys vesicularis* Simon, 1889 species inquirenda**

Poltys vesicularis Simon, 1889: 225 (imm.).

Distribution. Madagascar.

Family Clubionidae Simon, 1878***Clubiona guianensis* Caporiacco, 1947 species inquirenda**

Clubiona guianensis Caporiacco, 1947a: 27 (imm. ♂).

Distribution. Guyana.

***Clubiona sparassella* Strand, 1909 species inquirenda**

Clubiona sparassella Strand, 1909: 582 (imm.).

Distribution. South Africa.

Family Corinnidae Karsch, 1880***Castianeira brunellii* Caporiacco, 1940 species inquirenda**

Castianeira brunellii Caporiacco, 1940: 842 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

***Castianeira drassodoides* Strand, 1915 species inquirenda**

Castianeira drassodoides Strand, 1915: 162 (imm.).

Distribution. Israel.

***Castianeira inquinata* (Thorell, 1890) species inquirenda**

Agroeca inquinata Thorell, 1890: 352 (imm.).

Castianeira inquinata: Simon 1897: 167.

Agroeca inquinatum: Deeleman-Reinhold 2001: 346.

Distribution. Sumatra.

***Cycais gracilis* Karsch, 1879 species inquirenda**

Cycais gracilis Karsch, 1879: 95, pl. 1, figs. 15 (imm.).

Distribution. Japan.

***Scorteccia termitarum* Caporiacco, 1936 species inquirenda**

Scorteccia termitarum Caporiacco, 1936: 84 (imm.).

Distribution. Libya.

Remarks. Type species of *Scorteccia* Caporiacco, 1936.

Family Ctenidae Keyserling, 1877***Wiedenmeyeria falconensis* Schenkel, 1953 species inquirenda**

Wiedenmeyeria falconensis Schenkel, 1953a: 39 (imm. ♂).

Distribution. Venezuela.

Remarks. Type species of *Wiedenmeyeria* Schenkel, 1953.

Family Cybaeidae Banks, 1892

Cybaeus bronii* Caporiacco, 1934 *species inquirenda

Cybaeus bronii Caporiacco, 1934: 224 (imm.).

Distribution. Mongolia.

Family Dictynidae O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871

Hoplothys aethiopica* Caporiacco, 1947 *species inquirenda

Hoplothys aethiopica Caporiacco, 1947b: 102 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Remarks. Type species of *Hoplothys* Caporiacco, 1947.

Family Gnaphosidae Banks, 1892

Berlandina kolosvaryi* Caporiacco, 1947 *species inquirenda

Berlandina kolosvaryi Caporiacco, 1947b: 190 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Echemus scutatus* (Simon, 1880) *species inquirenda

Leptodrassus scutatus Simon, 1880: 262 (imm.).

Echemus scutatus: Dalmat 1919: 249.

Distribution. Algeria.

Ladissa semirufa* Simon, 1907 *species inquirenda

Ladissa semirufa Simon, 1907b: 238 (imm.).

Distribution. Benin.

Leptodrassus tropicus* Dalmat, 1919 *species inquirenda

Leptodrassus tropicus Dalmat, 1919: 247 (imm.).

Distribution. Sierra Leone.

Poecilochroa pauciaculeis* Caporiacco, 1947 *species inquirenda

Poecilochroa pauciaculeis Caporiacco, 1947b: 187 (imm.).

Distribution. Eritrea.

Pterotrichina nova* Caporiacco, 1934 *species inquirenda

Pterotrichina nova Caporiacco, 1934: 141 (imm.).

Distribution. Mongolia.

Scotophaeus lamperti* Strand, 1906 *species inquirenda

Scotophaeus lamperti Strand, 1906: 28 (imm.).

Distribution. Namibia.

Talanites ornatus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1874) *species inquirenda

Drassus ornatus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1874: 388 (imm.).

Talanites ornatus: Reimoser 1919: 164.

Distribution. Egypt.

Family Liocranidae Simon, 1897

***Oedignatha ferox* (Thorell, 1897) species inquirenda**

Aepygnatha ferox Thorell, 1897: 201 (imm.).

Oedignatha ferox: Simon 1897: 190.

Aepignatha ferox: Bonnet 1955: 176.

Distribution. Myanmar.

Family Lycosidae Sundevall, 1833

***Allocosa tenebrosa* (Thorell, 1897) species inquirenda**

Tarentula tenebrosa Thorell, 1897: 24 (imm.).

Allocosa tenebrosa: Roewer 1955b: 205.

Distribution. Myanmar.

***Arctosa nyembeensis* (Strand, 1916) species inquirenda**

Tarentula nyembeensis Strand, 1916: 113 (imm.).

Trochosa nyembeensis: Caporiacco 1949: 337.

Arctosa nyembeensis: Roewer 1955b: 229.

Distribution. Kenya and Tanzania.

***Artoria lycosimorpha* Strand, 1909 species inquirenda**

Artoria lycosimorpha Strand, 1909: 589 (imm.).

Artoriella lycosimorpha: Roewer 1955b: 233.

Artoriella lycosimorpha: Roewer 1960: 564, fig. 327 (imm.).

Distribution. South Africa.

***Geolycosa suahela* (Strand, 1913) species inquirenda**

Tarentula suahela Strand, 1913: 429 (imm.).

Lycorma suahela: Roewer 1955b: 266.

Geolycosa suahela: Roewer 1960: 712.

Distribution. Democratic Republic of the Congo.

***Hippasa flavicoma* Caporiacco, 1935 species inquirenda**

Hippasa flavicoma Caporiacco, 1935a: 230 (imm.).

Distribution. Mongolia.

***Hogna juanensis* (Strand, 1907) species inquirenda**

Tarentula juanensis Strand, 1907a: 744 (imm.).

Hogna juanensis: Caporiacco 1949: 337.

Distribution. Mozambique.

***Hogna truculenta* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876) species inquirenda**

Tarentula truculenta O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876: 601 (imm.).

Hogna truculenta: Roewer 1955b: 250.

Distribution. Egypt.

***Lycosa accurata* (Becker, 1886) species inquirenda**

Pardosa accurata Becker, 1886: 24 (imm.).

Lycosa accurata: Dondale & Redner 1984: 70.

Distribution. Mexico.

***Lycosa contestata* Montgomery, 1903 species inquirenda**

Lycosa contestata Montgomery, 1903: 649, pl. 29, fig. 4 (imm.).

Trochosa contestata: Montgomery 1904: 303.

Trochosa pratensis: Chamberlin 1909: 376 (misidentification).

Lycosa contestata: Brady 1980: 171.

Distribution. United States.

***Lycosa pavlovi* Schenkel, 1953 species inquirenda**

Lycosa pavlovi Schenkel, 1953a: 70 (imm.).

Distribution. China.

***Lycosa russea* Schenkel, 1953 species inquirenda**

Lycosa russea Schenkel, 1953a: 68 (imm.).

Distribution. China.

***Lycosa similis* Banks, 1892 species inquirenda**

Lycosa similis Banks, 1892: 64, pl. 2, fig. 30 (imm.).

Hogna helluo: Chamberlin 1908: 226 (misidentification).

Trochosa pratensis: Banks 1916: 80 (misidentification).

Lycosa similis: Brady 1980: 171.

Distribution. United States.

***Pardosa glabra* Mello-Leitão, 1938 species inquirenda**

Pardosa glabra Mello-Leitão, 1938: 95 (imm.).

Distribution. Argentina.

***Pardosa serena* (L. Koch, 1875) species inquirenda**

Lycosa serena L. Koch, 1875: 71 (imm.).

Pardosa serena: Roewer 1955b: 173.

Distribution. Egypt.

***Trochosa praetecta* L. Koch, 1875 species inquirenda**

Trochosa praetecta L. Koch, 1875: 75, pl. 7, fig. 3 (imm.).

Crocodilosa praetecta: Roewer 1955b: 238.

Trochosomma praetecta Roewer 1960: 855, fig. 475 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Family Miturgidae Simon, 1886

***Syspira pallida* Banks, 1904 species inquirenda**

Syspira pallida Banks, 1904: 111 (imm.).

Distribution. United States.

Family Oecobiidae Blackwall, 1862***Urocteana poecilis* Roewer, 1961 *species inquirenda***

Urocteana poecilis Roewer, 1961: 39, figs. 4a-c (imm.).

Distribution. Senegal.

Remarks. Type species of *Urocteana* Roewer, 1961.

Family Oxyopidae Thorell, 1869***Oxyopes annulipes* Thorell, 1890 *species inquirenda***

Oxyopes annulipes Thorell, 1890: 141 (imm.).

Distribution. Sumatra.

Oxyopes caporiaccoi* Roewer, 1951 *species inquirenda

Oxyopes incertus Caporiacco, 1939: 334 (imm., preoccupied name).

Oxyopes caporiaccoi Roewer, 1951: 442.

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Oxyopes concoloratus* Roewer, 1951 *species inquirenda

Oxyopes concolor Caporiacco, 1939: 339 (imm., preoccupied name).

Oxyopes concoloratus Roewer 1951: 442 (replacement name).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Family Philodromidae Thorell, 1869***Philodromus bigibba* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876) *species inquirenda***

Artanes bigibba O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876: 590 (imm. ♀).

Philodromus bigibba: Simon 1907a: 7.

Distribution. Algeria, Egypt, India, Sudan, and Yemen.

Philodromus borana* Caporiacco, 1939 *species inquirenda

Philodromus borana Caporiacco, 1939: 358 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Philodromus lugens* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876) *species inquirenda

Artanes lugens O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876: 591 (imm.).

Philodromus lugens: Lessert 1919: 185.

Distribution. Egypt.

Philodromus maculato vittatus* Strand, 1906 *species inquirenda

Philodromus maculato-vittatus Strand, 1906: 684 (imm.).

Philodromus maculato vittatus: Strand 1908l: 39, pl. 2, fig. 6 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Philodromus thanatellus* Strand, 1909 *species inquirenda

Philodromus thanatellus Strand, 1909: 580 (imm.).

Distribution. South Africa.

***Thanatus zavattarii* Caporiacco, 1939 species inquirenda**

Thanatus zavattarii Caporiacco, 1939: 359 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Family Pisauridae Simon, 1890

***Architis amazonica* (Simon, 1898) species inquirenda**

Nilus amazonicus Simon, 1898f: 17 (imm.).

Architis amazonica: Jäger 2011: 7, figs. 16–17 (imm.).

Distribution. Brazil.

***Hygropoda longitarsis* (Thorell, 1877) species inquirenda**

Dendrolycosa longitarsis Thorell, 1877: 525 (imm.).

Distribution. Sulawesi and Vietnam.

Remarks. The disjunct type localities suggest that the material from each respective site is unlikely to be conspecific.

***Hygropoda longitarsis fasciata* (Thorell, 1877) species inquirenda**

Dendrolycosa longitarsis fasciatum Thorell, 1877: 528 (imm.).

Distribution. Sulawesi.

Remarks. It is most strange that Thorell felt the need to describe and distinguish a subspecies based on a juvenile from another species based on a juvenile.

***Stoliczka affinis* Caporiacco, 1935 species inquirenda**

Stoliczka affinis Caporiacco, 1935a: 229 (imm.).

Distribution. Pakistan.

***Tapinothelella laboriosa* Strand, 1909 species inquirenda**

Tapinothelella laboriosa Strand, 1909: 586 (imm.).

Distribution. South Africa.

Remarks. Type species of *Tapinothelella* Strand, 1909.

***Tapinothelops vittipes* (Caporiacco, 1941) species inquirenda**

Tapinothele vittipes Caporiacco, 1941: 54 (imm.).

Tapinothelops vittipes: Roewer 1955a: 395.

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Family Prodidomidae Simon, 1884

***Prodidomus tigrinus* Dalmas, 1919 species inquirenda**

Prodidomus tigrinus Dalmas, 1919: 306 (imm.).

Distribution. Sierra Leone.

Family Scytodidae Blackwall, 1864

***Scytodes constellata* Lawrence, 1938 species inquirenda**

Scytodes constellata Lawrence, 1938a: 472, fig. 9 (imm.).

Scytodes constellata: Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2021: 12, 4 unnumbered figs. (imm.).

Distribution. South Africa.

Scytodes quinqua* Lawrence, 1927 *species inquirenda

Scytodes quinqua Lawrence, 1927: 8, pl. 3, fig. 73 (imm.).

Scytodes quinqua: Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2021: 28, 2 unnumbered figs. (imm.).

Distribution. South Africa.

Family Senoculidae Simon, 1890

Senoculus guianensis* Caporiacco, 1947 *species inquirenda

Senoculus guianensis Caporiacco, 1947a: 23 (imm.).

Distribution. Guyana.

Family Tetragnathidae Menge, 1866

Leucauge fishoekensis* Strand, 1909 *species inquirenda

Leucauge fishoekensis Strand, 1909: 571 (imm.).

Distribution. South Africa.

Tetragnatha aetherea* (Simon, 1895) *species inquirenda

Prionolaema aetherea Simon, 1894: 725 (unavailable name).

Prionolaema aetherea Simon 1895: 150 (imm.).

Tetragnatha aetherea: Dimitrov, Álvarez-Padilla & Hormiga 2008: 53, figs. 2A-B (imm.).

Tetragnatha aetherea: Castanheira & Baptista 2021: 654 (species inquirenda).

Distribution. Venezuela.

Remarks. This species was already proposed as a *species inquirenda* by Castanheira & Baptista (2021), I agree with them and that it is better not considered a *nomen dubium* as topotypic material could be collected.

Tetragnatha caffra* (Strand, 1909) *species inquirenda

Eucta caffra Strand, 1909: 569 (imm.).

Distribution. South Africa.

Family Theridiidae Sundevall, 1833

Argyrodes vatovae* (Caporiacco, 1940) *species inquirenda

Argyrodina vatovae Caporiacco, 1940: 817, figs. 27 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Dipoena bristowei* Caporiacco, 1949 *species inquirenda

Dipoena bristowei Caporiacco, 1949: 377 (imm.).

Distribution. Kenya.

Dipoena seminigra* Simon, 1909 *species inquirenda

Dipoena seminigra Simon, 1909: 94.

Distribution. Vietnam.

Episinus mucronatus* (Simon, 1894) *species inquirenda

Penictis mucronata Simon, 1894: 520 (imm.).

Distribution. Singapore.

***Euryopis campestrata* Simon, 1907 species inquirenda**

Euryopis campestrata Simon, 1907a: 5 (imm.).

Distribution. Egypt.

***Euryopis venutissima* (Caporiacco, 1934) species inquirenda**

Philarcus venutissimus Caporiacco, 1934: 143, pl. 4, fig. 3 (imm.).

Distribution. Mongolia.

***Janula modesta* (Thorell, 1898) species inquirenda**

Janulus modestus Thorell, 1898: 292 (imm.).

Distribution. Myanmar.

***Theridion albidorsum* Strand, 1909 species inquirenda**

Theridion albidorsum Strand, 1909: 561 (imm.).

Distribution. South Africa.

***Theridion albomaculosum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1869 species inquirenda**

Theridion albomaculosum O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1869: 386, pl. 12, figs. 57–60 (imm.).

Distribution. Sri Lanka.

***Theridion angustifrons* Caporiacco, 1934 species inquirenda**

Theridion angustifrons Caporiacco, 1934: 148 (imm.).

Distribution. Mongolia.

***Theridion astrigerum* Thorell, 1895 species inquirenda**

Theridion astrigerum Thorell, 1895: 99 (imm.).

Distribution. Myanmar.

***Theridion fornicatum* Simon, 1884 species inquirenda**

Theridion fornicatum Simon, 1884: 22 (imm.).

Distribution. Sudan.

***Theridion latisternum* Caporiacco, 1934 species inquirenda**

Theridion latisternum Caporiacco, 1934: 148, pl. 1, fig. 16 (imm.).

Distribution. Mongolia.

***Theridion meneghettii* Caporiacco, 1949 species inquirenda**

Theridion meneghettii Caporiacco, 1949: 390 (imm.).

Distribution. Kenya.

***Theridion octoferum* Strand, 1909 species inquirenda**

Theridion octoferum Strand, 1909: 560 (imm.).

Distribution. South Africa.

***Theridion quadripapulatum* Thorell, 1895 species inquirenda**

Theridion quadripapulatum Thorell, 1895: 91 (imm.).

Distribution. Myanmar.

***Theridion teutanooides* Caporiacco, 1949 species inquirenda**

Theridion teutanooides Caporiacco, 1949: 385 (imm.).

Distribution. Kenya.

Family Thomisidae Sundevall, 1833***Borboropactus noditarsis* (Simon, 1903) species inquirenda**

Regillus noditarsis Simon, 1903: 101 (imm.).

Borboropactus noditarsis: Roewer 1955a: 752.

Distribution. Presumably West Africa, no country of origin stated.

***Cyriogonus triquetrus* Simon, 1886 species inquirenda**

Cyriogonus triquetrus Simon, 1886: 177 (imm.).

Distribution. Madagascar.

***Cyriogonus vinsonii* (Thorell, 1875) species inquirenda**

Misumena vinsonii Thorell, 1875: 146 (imm.).

Cyriogonus vinsoni: Lessert 1919: 171.

Cynathea vinsoni: Roewer 1955c: 831.

Cyriogonus vinsoni: Lehtinen 2004: 159.

Distribution. Madagascar.

***Diaea pogneti* Simon, 1886 species inquirenda**

Diaea pogneti Simon, 1886: 460 (imm.).

Distribution. India.

Remarks. The paper of Simon (1886) was for over a century frequently cited by workers as having been published in 1885. For the date of publication, refer to the excellent publication by Frétey (2023).

***Erissus sanctaeleopoldinae* (B. A. M. Soares & H. E. M. Soares, 1946) species inquirenda**

Stephanopoides sanctaeleopoldinae Soares & Soares, 1946: 55, figs. 3–4 (imm.).

Erissus sanctaeleopoldinae: Bonaldo & Lise 2001: 67.

Distribution. Brazil.

***Firmicus lentiginosus* (Simon, 1886) species inquirenda**

Synaema lentiginosum Simon, 1886: 180 (imm.).

Firmicus lentiginosus: Simon 1932: 786.

Firmicus lentiginosus: Lessert 1943: 321.

Distribution. Africa, type locality “Zambeze” (Simon, 1886: 180) likely refers to the river which runs through a number of modern countries.

***Firmicus strandi* Caporiacco, 1947 species inquirenda**

Firmicus strandi Caporiacco, 1947a: 220 (imm.).

Distribution. Tanzania.

***Heriaesynaema flavipes* Caporiacco, 1939 species inquirenda**

Heriaesynaema flavipes Caporiacco, 1939: 368, fig. 20 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

Remarks. Type species of *Heriaesynaema* Caporiacco, 1939.

***Hexommulocymus kolosvaryi* Caporiacco, 1955 species inquirenda**

Hexommulocymus kolosvaryi Caporiacco, 1955: 410, fig. 61 (imm.).

Distribution. Venezuela.

Remarks. Type species of *Hexommulocymus* Caporiacco, 1955.

***Holopelus irroratus* (Thorell, 1899) species inquirenda**

Bomis irrorata Thorell, 1899: 73 (imm.).

Holopelus irroratus: Simon 1907b: 314.

Distribution. Cameroon.

***Monaeses cinerascens* (Thorell, 1887) species inquirenda**

Rhynchognatha cinerascens Thorell, 1887: 285 (imm.).

Monaeses cinerascens: Simon 1895: 993.

Rhynchognatha cinerascens: Crome 1962: 168.

Distribution. Myanmar and Sri Lanka.

Remarks. I am rather doubtful that the material from these respective disjunct countries can be conspecific.

***Phrynarachne fatalis* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1899 species inquirenda**

Phrynarachne fatalis O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1899: 525, pl. 30, fig. 70 (imm.).

Distribution. Sri Lanka.

***Synema cervinum* Schenkel, 1936 species inquirenda**

Synema cervina Schenkel, 1936: 137 (imm.).

Synema cervinum Roewer 1955b: 885.

Distribution. China.

***Synema pauciaculeis* Caporiacco, 1947 species inquirenda**

Synema pauciaculeis Caporiacco, 1947a: 224 (imm.).

Distribution. Tanzania.

***Synema quadrifasciatum* Dahl, 1907 species inquirenda**

Synaema (Rimania) quadrifasciata Dahl, 1907: 381, 392 (imm.).

Distribution. Tanzania.

Remarks. Subgenera (e.g. *Rimania* Dahl, 1907) are essentially rejected by most in modern arachnology, therefore comments on subgenera are not presented in this work.

***Synema scalare* Strand, 1913 species inquirenda**

Synema scalare Strand, 1913: 396 (imm.).

Distribution. Uganda.

***Tharrhalea cerussata* Simon, 1886 species inquirenda**

Tharrhalea cerussata Simon, 1886: 183 (imm.).

Distribution. Madagascar.

***Thomisus litoris* Strand, 1913 species inquirenda**

Thomisus litoris Strand, 1913: 394 (imm.).

Distribution. Democratic Republic of the Congo and/or Uganda.

Remarks. The type locality is a lake that expands either side of the border of the above two countries.

***Thomisus melanostethus* Simon, 1909 species inquirenda**

Thomisus melanostethus Simon, 1909: 140 (imm.).

Distribution. Vietnam.

***Tmarus bisectus* Piza, 1944 species inquirenda**

Tmarus bisectus Piza, 1944: 270, fig. 5 (imm.).

Distribution. Brazil.

Remarks. Only one of the two immature female syntypes is present in IBSP where the Piza collection of types originally deposited in the Museu de Zoologia da “Luiz de Queiroz” Piracicaba, Brazil now reside (Antonio Brescovit pers. comm.). Therefore, the other immature female syntype must be considered lost at the present time.

***Xysticus barbatus* Caporiacco, 1936 species inquirenda**

Xysticus barbatus Caporiacco, 1936: 115 (imm.).

Distribution. Libya.

***Xysticus beni* Strand, 1913 species inquirenda**

Xysticus beni Strand, 1913: 395 (imm.).

Distribution. Democratic Republic of the Congo.

***Xysticus multiaculeatus* Caporiacco, 1940 species inquirenda**

Xysticus multiaculeatus Caporiacco, 1940: 849 (imm.).

Distribution. Ethiopia.

***Xysticus simonstownensis* Strand, 1909 species inquirenda**

Xysticus simonstownensis Strand, 1909: 576 (imm.).

Distribution. South Africa.

Family Udubidae Griswold & Polotow, 2015***Raecius aculeatus* Dahl, 1901 species inquirenda**

Raecius aculeatus Dahl, 1901: 188 (imm.).

“*Racius*” *aculeatus*: Griswold 2002: 129.

Distribution. Democratic Republic of the Congo.

Family Uloboridae Thorell, 1869***Uloborus albolineatus* Mello-Leitão, 1941 species inquirenda**

Uloborus albolineatus Mello-Leitão, 1941: 111 (imm. ♂).

Distribution. Argentina.

Family Xenoctenidae Ramírez & Silva-Dávila, 2017***Odo drescoi* (Caporiacco, 1955) species inquirenda**

Horioctenus drescoi Caporiacco, 1955: 399 (imm.).

Odo drescoi: Brignoli 1983: 590.

Distribution. Venezuela.

***Odo incertus* Caporiacco, 1955 species inquirenda**

Odo incertus Caporiacco, 1955: 400 (imm.).

Distribution. Venezuela.

Family Zoropsidae Bertkau, 1882

***Zoropsis beccarii* Caporiacco, 1935 species inquirenda**

Zoropsis beccarii Caporiacco, 1935a: 285 (imm.).

Distribution. Turkey.

● **Species described from juvenile stowaway material**

Schmidt (1956a, b) described a number of species from imported specimens found primarily in produce from Latin America and Africa. Most were described from adults and are not relevant here, but the following species below were described from juveniles. All are deposited in the Senckenberg Forschungsinstitut und Naturmuseum, Frankfurt am Main, Germany.

Fruit importation from around the world often results in spiders being found as stowaways in the Northern Hemisphere, and in some cases the supposed origin of the fruit can either erroneous or may be imported from more than one country without ability to differentiate which export the specimen truly arrived on (Sherwood & Alayón Garcíá 2022, 2023; Sherwood in press). Thus, whilst in theory these specimens could be DNA sequenced to try and aid in their identification, given that their supposed countries of origin are not guaranteed to be correct, I prefer to render them as *nomina dubia*.

Family Philodromidae Thorell, 1869

***Gephyrota viridipallida* Schmidt, 1956 nomen dubium**

Cephyrota [lapsus for *Gephyrota*] *viridipallida* Schmidt, 1956a: 27 (imm.).

Supposed country of origin. Cameroon.

Family Pisauridae Simon, 1890

***Conakrya wolffi* Schmidt, 1956 nomen dubium**

Conakrya wolffi Schmidt, 1956b: 240 (imm.).

Supposed country of origin. Guinea.

Family Thomisidae Sundevall, 1833

***Carcinarachne* Schmidt, 1956 nomen dubium**

Carcinarachne Schmidt, 1956a: 26.

Remarks. Resultant from its type species being rendered a *nomen dubium* (see below).

***Carcinarachne brocki* Schmidt, 1956 nomen dubium**

Carcinarachne brocki Schmidt, 1956a: 26, fig. 1 (imm.).

Supposed country of origin. Ecuador.

Family Uloboridae Thorell, 1869

Uloborus plumosus Schmidt, 1956 *nomen dubium*

Uloborus plumosus Schmidt, 1956a: 25 (imm.).

Supposed country of origin. Guinea.

● Subspecies in spiders

Many subspecies below are raised to species rank, as their genitalia is sufficiently different from each other, and this morphological evidence coupled with biogeographical evidence supports the hypothesis they each are independently evolving lineages (de Quieroz 2007). All are supported by excellent illustrations in the respective publications, which allow for such a rapid judgement. This is not a comprehensive list of all spider subspecies which are likely good species, many others require revision of type material or collection of topotypes due to poor-quality, or even absence, of illustrations; they are not considered here. Also excluded are taxa which I know that colleagues or students intend to work on in the near future. It is particularly puzzling why the untenable concept of a subspecies (Burbrink *et al.* 2022; see also below) was applied heavily within one particular agelenid group, because despite close ranges of species, the genitalic characters to distinguish them are stable and in no other genus is such amounts of variation considered to be below the species level. Several synonymies with nominate species are given for other taxa, and one subspecies is, for now only, proposed as a *subspecies inquirenda*, as I respond directly to the arguments by two colleagues who recently argued that subspecies were tenable in spiders.

Taxa with new or restored species status

Family Araneidae Clerck, 1757

Alpaida audiberti Dierkens, 2014 *stat. rev.*

Alpaida monzon audiberti Dierkens, 2014: 17, figs. 11–12, 43 (♀).

Remarks. This taxon is extremely disjunct from the nominate species in Peru, being from French Guiana. There are also differences in the size of the copulatory openings and the shape on the lateral sides of the scape (see Dierkens 2014). Combined, these are sufficient evidence to consider it a separate species.

Family Agelenidae C. L. Koch, 1837

Coelotes alatauensis Ovtchinnikov, 2000 *stat. rev.*

Coelotes curvilamnis alatauensis Ovtchinnikov, 2000: 42, figs. 25–28 (♂♀).

Distribution. Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan.

Remarks. The differences in the shape of the male palp and female epigyne, as with all other congeners dealt with here, differentiate this species from other former subspecies with which it was related.

Coelotes boomensis Ovtchinnikov, 2000 *stat. rev.*

Coelotes curvilamnis boomensis Ovtchinnikov, 2000: 42, figs. 21–24 (♂♀).

Distribution. Kyrgyzstan.

Remarks. As for *C. alatauensis*, the genitalia of this taxon is distinct in comparison to congeners.

Coelotes carpathensis Ovtchinnikov, 1999 *stat. rev.*

Coelotes pastor carpathensis Ovtchinnikov, 1999: 72, figs. 28–31 (♂♀).

Coelotes pickardi carpathensis: Isaia & Pantini 2009: 24.

Distribution. Ukraine.

Remarks. As for *C. alatauensis*, the genitalia of this taxon is distinct in comparison to congeners.

***Coelotes pastor* Simon, 1875 stat. rest.**

Coelotes pastor Simon, 1875: 38, pl. 5, fig. 12 (♂♀).

Coelotes pastor: Kulczyński 1887: 274, 342, pl. 8, fig. 60 (♂).

Amaurobius pastor: Kulczyński 1906: 454, pl. 14, figs. 6, 9–10, pl. 15, figs. 36, 52, 58 (♂♀).

Coelotes pastor: Simon 1937: 986, 989, 1035, figs. 1512, 1519 (♂♀).

Coelotes pastor: Drensky 1942: 43, fig. 9a (♀).

Coelotes pastor: de Blauwe 1973a: 81, figs. 71–74 (♂♀).

Coelotes pastor: de Blauwe 1973b: 267, figs. 1–11 (♀).

Coelotes pastor: de Blauwe 1975: 146, figs. 1–2 (♀).

Coelotes pastor: Maurer 1982: 166, figs. 2a, 3, 4a (♀).

Coelotes pastor: Trotta 2005: 161, fig. 201 (♀).

Coelotes pickardi pastor: Isaia & Pantini 2009: 25, fig. 2a (♂).

Distribution. France.

Remarks. As for *C. alatauensis*, the genitalia of this taxon is distinct in comparison to congeners.

***Coelotes tirolensis* (Kulczyński, 1906) stat. rev.**

Amaurobius pickardi tirolensis Kulczyński, 1906b: 458, pl. 14, figs. 11, 13 (♀).

Coelotes pastor tirolensis: Drensky 1942: 43, fig. 9b (♀).

Coelotes pastor tirolensis: Tystshenko 1971: 160, fig. 451 (♀).

Coelotes pastor tirolensis: Maurer 1982a: 319, figs. 1a–c (♂♀).

Coelotes pastor tirolensis: Maurer 1982b: 172, figs. 1d, 2b (♀).

Coelotes pastor lessinensis: Maurer 1982b: 174, figs. 5a–b (♂♀).

Coelotes pastor tirolensis: Wang 2002: 42.

Coelotes pickardi tirolensis: Isaia & Pantini 2009: 26, fig. 2d (♂).

Coelotes pickardi tirolensis: Chen, Zhao & Li 2016b: 54, figs. 1A–C, 2A–E (♂♀).

Distribution. Italy, Switzerland, and possibly Ukraine.

Remarks. As for *C. alatauensis*, the genitalia of this taxon is distinct in comparison to congeners.

***Coelotes ketmenensis* Ovtchinnikov, 2000 stat. rev.**

Coelotes striatilanis ketmenensis Ovtchinnikov, 2000: 44, figs. 33–34 (♀).

Distribution. Kazakhstan.

Remarks. As for *C. alatauensis*, the genitalia of this taxon is distinct in comparison to congeners.

Family Thomisidae Sundevall, 1833

***Ozyptila canadensis* Dondale & Redner, 1975 stat. rev.**

Ozyptila bryantae: Gertsch, 1939: 348 (♂, misidentification).

Ozyptila sincera canadensis Dondale & Redner 1975: 150, figs. 17, 20, 41, 64–66 (♂♀).

Ozyptila sincera canadensis: Dondale & Redner 1978: 163, figs. 418, 422, 503–507 (♂♀).

Ozyptila sincera canadensis: Paquin & Dupérré 2003: 230, figs. 2578–2581 (♂♀).

Distribution. Canada and United States.

Remarks. The genitalia of this spider are well-illustrated (see Dondale & Redner 1975, 1978) and there is nothing to suggest the differences are anything other than interspecific. Thus, this taxon is raised to species level.

***Ozyptila oraria* Dondale & Redner, 1975 stat. rest.**

Ozyptila sincera oraria Dondale & Redner, 1975: 151, figs. 18, 21, 67–71 (♂♀).

Ozyptila oraria: Ono 1988: 127.

Distribution. United States.

Remarks. Ono (1988) already considered *O. oraria* to be a good species but this was seemingly overlooked by most later workers. I agree with him that this species is distinct based on genitalic morphology. Thus, this taxon is raised to species level.

New synonyms

Family Linyphiidae Blackwall, 1859

***Diplocephalus connatus* Bertkau, 1889 = *Diplocephalus connatus jacksonii* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904 syn. nov.**

Diplocephalus jacksonii O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904: 166, pl. A, figs. 9–9a (♂♀).

Diplocephalus jacksoni: Locket & Millidge 1953: 295, fig. 177F (♂).

Diplocephalus connatus jacksoni: Roberts 1987: 86, fig. 391 (♂, as “form” not subspecies).

Synonymy list given for junior synonym only, for senior name, see World Spider Catalog (2024).

Remarks. It has long been accepted in Britain that *Diplocephalus connatus jacksonii* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904 is synonymous with *D. connatus* Bertkau, 1889 but Roberts (1987) simply downgraded it to a “form”, which had no real taxonomic meaning in the modern era. This means it has remained as a subspecies until now, as seen on the World Spider Catalog (2024). Therefore, I propose *Diplocephalus connatus jacksoni* **syn. nov.** as a junior synonym of *D. connatus*.

***Gnathonarium dentatum* (Wider, 1834) = *Gnathonarium dentata orientalis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872) syn. nov.**

Erigone dentata orientalis O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872: 290 (♂♀).

Synonymy list given for junior synonym only, for senior name, see World Spider Catalog (2024).

Remarks. I have been unable to locate the type material of the Israeli subspecies *Gnathonarium dentatum orientale* (O. Pickard-Cambridge 1872) in OUMNH and thus it is assumed lost. The description gives no characters which unambiguously differentiate it from its nominate species (World Spider Catalog 2024). Therefore, I propose *Gnathonarium dentatum orientale* **syn. nov.** as a junior synonym of *G. dentatum*, a species is widely distributed in Europe and the Middle East (World Spider Catalog 2024).

***Pityohyphantes costatus* Hentz, 1850 = *Pityohyphantes costatus annulipes* (Banks, 1892) syn. nov.**

Linyphia costata Hentz, 1850: 31, pl. 4, fig. 11 (♀).

Linyphia phrygiana: Emerton 1882: 63, pl. 19, figs. 1a–h (♂♀, misidentification).

Linyphia phrygiana: Keyserling 1886: 60, pl. 12, fig. 164 (♂♀, misidentification).

Linyphia phrygianus annulipes Banks, 1892: 42. **syn. nov.**

Linyphia phrygiana: Emerton 1902: 141, figs. 332–334 (♂♀, misidentification).

Linyphia phrygiana: Comstock 1910: 171, figs. 10–11 (♂, misidentification).

Linyphia phrygiana: Comstock 1912: 394, figs. 407–409 (♂♀, misidentification).

Pityohyphantes phrygianus: Blauvelt 1936: 137, pl. 12, figs. 80–84, 86 (♂♀, misidentification).

Linyphia phrygiana: Comstock 1940: 112, 408, figs. 102–103, 379, 386 (♂, misidentification).

Pityohyphantes phrygianus: Muma 1943: 81, pl. XIII, figs. 13–14 (♂♀, misidentification).

Pityohyphantes costatus: Chamberlin & Ivie 1943: 28.

Pityohyphantes phrygianus: Kaston 1948: 119, figs. 240–248 (♂♀, misidentification).

Pityohyphantes costatus: Kaston 1972: 125, figs. 16, 282–283 (♂♀).

Pityohyphantes costatus: Paquin & Dupérré 2003: 146, figs. 1615–1617 (♂♀).

Remarks. Banks (1892: 42) states this subspecies is a “little smaller” than the nominate species *P. phrygianus* (C. L. Koch, 1836) and uses differences in colouration to differentiate it. The type locality of this United States spider is Fall Creek, New York State. The whereabouts of the type material is unknown, it is not registered as being present in MCZ, where the vast majority of Bank’s type material is housed. Therefore, only the description is available to identify this taxon. *Pityohyphantes costatus* is known to occur in New York, including the general area of the type locality of *P. costatus annulipes*, and the colouration and slight difference in body size of the subspecies can be explained by intraspecific variation. Therefore, I propose *Pityohyphantes costatus annulipes* **syn. nov.** as a junior synonym of *P. costatus*.

Family Theridiidae Sundevall, 1833

Steatoda grossa (C. L. Koch, 1838) = *Steatoda grossa strandi* (Ermolajev, 1934) **syn. nov.**

Teutana grossa strandi Ermolajev, 1934: 145.

Synonymy list given for junior synonym only, for senior name, see World Spider Catalog (2024).

Remarks. The type material of this Russian species is lost (Kiril Mikhailov pers. comm.) but the description is sufficiently detailed to recognise it as belonging to the nominate species, which occurs widely in Siberia. The differences mentioned in the description are insufficient to justify its separation. Therefore, I propose *S. grossa strandi* **syn. nov.** as a synonym of *S. grossa*.

Family Thomisidae Sundevall, 1833

Synema globosum (Fabricius, 1775) = *Synema globosum nigriventre* Kulczyński, 1901 **syn. nov.**

Synema globosum nigriventris Kulczyński, 1901: 336, pl. 13, figs. 6–7 (♀).

Synema globosum nigriventre: Roewer 1955b: 886.

Synema japonicum nigriventris: Utochkin 1960: 1019, figs. 5.1–4 (♂♀).

Synonymy list given for junior synonym only, for senior name, see World Spider Catalog (2024).

Remarks. Utochkin (1960) illustrated this Russian (Siberian) subspecies and transferred it as a taxon nominal to *Synema japonicum* Karsch, 1879 (itself now a junior synonym of *S. globosum*). However, this was not followed by most future workers. This subspecies easily falls within the intraspecific variation of *S. globosum* and no evidence like that existing for populations on the Canary Islands (see below) exists to suggest any significant differences to question whether it may be divergent. Therefore, I synonymise *S. globosum nigriventre* **syn. nov.** with *S. globosum*.

Subspecies inquirenda

Synema globosum canariense Dahl, 1907 *subspecies inquirenda*

Synema globosum canariense Dahl, 1907: 378.

Synema globosum: Wunderlich 1986: 252.

Synema globosum canariense: Lissner & Suárez 2023: 23, figs. 2–3 (♂♀, habitus).

Distribution. Canary Islands.

Remarks. Lissner & Suarez (2023) rely on the definitions of subspecies by Mayr (1963) and Monroe (1982) but do not discuss this in more detail. In addition to Mayr (1963), Mayr (as sole or co-author) provided more recent and equally extensive definitions for subspecies (e.g. Mayr 1965, 1969, 1982; O’Brien & Mayr 1991). Mayr also discussed the matter much earlier (Mayr 1940, 1954), even citing Mayr (1954) as the primary reference for his definition of subspecies in O’Brien & Mayr (1991). Perhaps Lissner & Suarez (2023) were unaware, but Monroe (1982) was one of 10 articles [excluding the editorial by John A. Weins, introducing this collection of papers: Weins (1982)] published in volume 9, part 2 of *The Auk*, where many varied opinions on the validity (or non-validity) of subspecies was discussed (i.e. Parkes 1982; Gill 1982; Storer 1982; Barrowclough 1982; Lanyon 1982; Zusi 1982;

Monroe 1982; O'Neill 1982; Phillips 1982), including a contemporaneous article by Mayr himself (Mayr, 1982).

Mayr (1982: 594) acknowledges that following the “*elaborate methodology*” he outlines in Mayr (1969) [six years after publication of the article used by Lissner & Suarez (2023) to define a subspecies] for subspecies met continued criticism. Tellingly, he states “*Hence, it became clear that the subspecies was not a concept of evolutionary biology but simply a handle of convenience for the clerical work of the museum curator. The subspecies was likewise found deficient when studied as the adaptive response to local environmental conditions. During the study of clines, workers found the more-or-less arbitrarily determined subspecies borders to be often more of a hindrance than a help, and those who studied geographic variation with biometric and multifactorial methods usually paid no attention to subspecies designations in their analyses of populations*”.

Whilst Mayr (1982) finished with justification for maintaining subspecies, the reasons he gives can be surmised as: (1) for curatorial convenience, and (2) for convenience of non-taxonomists studying populations. Neither of these are, in the present author’s opinion, sufficient reasons for the use of subspecies. Evolutionary relationships are not a matter of convenience for humans, they are a true reflection of the evolutionary process of life through space and time. Mayr would much later define the concept of subspecies without using the above arguments to justify it (i.e. O’Brien & Mayr 1991) but they do give a glimpse to his earlier mindset and how he and most others who used the rank in the Twentieth Century may have thought about subspecies.

Monroe (1983: 609) concludes his arguments for subspecies as: “*Subspecies (a trinomial scientific name) should be used in two situations: (1) allopatric populations where definition of the populations is clear, distinct, and total (or very nearly so); and (2) situations where secondary contact between distinct populations has occurred and the zone of intergradation is relatively narrow*”. The quote provided by Lissner & Suarez (2023) explicitly attributed to Monroe (1982) is misleading, as that wording appears nowhere in Monroe’s article, although it is a good way to summarise his argument.

Lissner & Suarez (2023: 23) write: “*Perhaps a more modern way of subdividing polytypic spider species into subspecies is the concept of superspecies with allospecies as subunits (Kraus 2002)*”. Whilst the topic of superspecies with allotypic units is one the present author thinks has merit, it is absolutely not a “... way of subdividing polytypic spider species into subspecies ...” and thus must be discussed in more depth below.

As discussed by Kraus (2002), who derives his definition of a superspecies from the original proposal of Mayr (1931) and the much more recent refinement of Mayr & Ashlock (1991), superspecies are groups of species (*not* subspecies), so this concept has nothing to do with nor justifies the establishment of subspecies. Instead, the superspecies concept – of particular relevance to spiders (Kraus 2002) – provides a basis to justify that distinct populations, even if not differentiating consistently in the primary taxonomic character of the genitalia, can be regarded as full species (allospecies grouped with other monophyletic taxa as a superspecies) if they meet certain criteria.

The use of the ornithological article of Monroe (1982) in particular as a justification for subspecies in spiders by Lissner & Suarez (2023) also demonstrates that they did not pay close attention to the argumentation of Kraus (2002), especially in his arguments about allopatric speciation in spiders and the comparatively rapid diversification of allopatric species in this group. Again, the superspecies concept is much better applied here, because often minute differences between allopatric populations are quantifiable, no matter how ‘insignificant’ the individual taxonomist considers a particular character (or characters) for use differentiating at the species-level.

Wunderlich (2008) also discussed the topic of subspecies (and other taxonomic ranks such as subgenera) more broadly in spiders, citing cases where he thought subspecies of certain taxa were not justified, and some where he provisionally thought they were, pending breeding experiments. This latter argumentation suggests that Wunderlich in his 2008 work and earlier, was strongly applying the Biological Species Concept. Through their citation of other works by Mayr, it can be deduced that this concept is also the primary one used by Lissner & Suarez (2023). As demonstrated by Burbrink *et al.* (2023), application of the Biological Species Concept to recognise subspecies often results in the grouping of paraphyletic taxa.

In spiders, the Biological Species Concept is not always the best line of evidence, as clearly morphologically, biogeographically, and molecularly different species are not always guaranteed to be unable to exchange genes (Kraus, 2002). The application of the Biological Species Concept to theraphosids, for instance, would render many clearly different sister species, which have distinct and constant differences in the genitalia and other somatic characters that justify their maintenance as individual and distinct lineages (*sensu* De Queiroz 2007), as conspecific because they have been demonstrably hybridised in captivity by pet hobbyists (see Cléton, Sigwalt & Verdez 2015). This can also be seen in many araneomorph taxa such as agelenids and lycosids, where closely related species (but with distinct quantifiable differences in the genitalia) can hybridise (e.g. Oxford 2019; Simó, Seguí & Pérez-Miles 2002).

Lissner & Suarez (2023) state: “*Subspecies or local geographic races represent conservation units of special interest, and in our opinion, they should have the same focus in conservation efforts as species since they have the potential to evolve into new species*”. This argumentation is not new. Given the arbitrary nature of subspecies, and the inconsistent criteria used to define them, emphasising their importance in conservation could have negative effects on the actual conservation of valid species (Burbrink *et al.* 2022). This argumentation by Lissner & Suarez (2023) can in part be related to arguments by Mayr (1982) discussed above, where the concept of a subspecies is justifiable as a tool of convenience and/or improving bureaucratic efficiency.

An extremely important point made by Lissner & Suarez (2023) is that a comprehensive prior investigation of molecular and morphological variability in *Synema globosum* (Fabricius, 1775) by Urfer *et al.* (2021) incorporated only *S. globosum s. s.* [as *S. globosum globosum* in Lissner & Suarez (2023)] and did not sample topotypic material of any of the prior-proposed subspecies of *S. globosum* (see World Spider Catalog 2023). Therefore, Urfer *et al.* (2021) provide very useful data on intraspecific variation within *S. globosum s. s.* but do not advance knowledge of the taxonomic position of any of the described subspecies.

Lissner & Suarez (2023) use this point to then justify as follows: “*Differences in both morphological features compared to mainland specimens as well as the monophyletic position of the Canarian specimens are sufficient arguments to resurrect the subspecies S. g. canariense*”. It is pertinent to examine these characters, which do seem valid, but do not justify relegating this taxon to a subspecific rank. Their diagnosis of *S. g. canariense* gives characters for delimitation: 1) carapace colouration, 2) sternum colouration, 3) near absence of intraspecific colour polymorphy, 4) opisthosoma not bicoloured and 5) foliaceous mark of opisthosoma never jet black. Lissner & Suarez (2023) found these characters to be diagnostic and stable in *S. g. canariense* and this is certainly not doubted by the present author. However, the (assumed) absence of genitalic characters to differentiate this lineage, and the fact the COI barcode distance is <2% (J. Lissner pers. comm.) is a complicating factor, and the urge to just immediately assume that there is simply low interspecific barcode gaps within this genus must be resisted. Thorough molecular investigation of material from the type localities of all subspecies (presently valid or synonymised) must be undertaken before any broad assumptions about genetic species limits in *Synema* are made. It is possible *S. g. canariense* will need to be elevated to species level in future, as morphology and preliminary molecular data suggest it may be diverging, but it is simply ‘not there yet’. The subspecies rank is generally unacceptable but will be maintained here as a temporary measure until it is clear whether it must be: (1) synonymised or (2) elevated, based on comprehensive molecular evidence. Therefore, I propose *Synema globosum canariense* as a **subspecies inquirenda**.

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